

ISic0642

I.Sicily inscription 0642

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2015.10.19

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Found in via Manzoni (in chiesa S. Nicoletta)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Soprintendenza stores

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332933

1. [ὁ δεῖνα ἐποίη]-
2. σεν ἐαυτῷ κὲ Ῥω[σ]-
3. κία Ἀντωνία τ[ῆ] συν-
4. συνβίω²⁶συνβίω²⁶ αὐτοῦ. □
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644884

PHI 332933

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1994.0765

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 44.0763

Manganaro, G. 1994. Iscrizioni, epigrafi ed epigrammi in Greco della Sicilia orientale di epoca romana. *Mélanges de l'École Française de Rome: Antiquité.* 106: 79-118. At 86-88 no.5 fig.8

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